

THE ROLE OF PEDAGOGICAL SKILLS IN EDUCATION AND USE OF NEW METHODS IN TEACHING PRINCIPLES

Turemuratova Aziza Begibaevna

Assistant, Department of Pedagogy and Psychology, Karakalpak State University
named after Berdakh, Republic of Karakalpakstan:

Sultanova Elvira Torebaevna

Student of Karakalpak State University:

Orazova Benezera Furxatovna

Student of Karakalpak State University:

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Abstract: Pedagogical skills in education are approaches to make higher education accessible and reasonable for all. Providing direction, appropriate materials and computer facilities for all teaching and learning systems is essential. The level of education in the twenty-first century will be higher than it was in the twentieth century because of these changes and expansions. Conditions are created to prepare students for the challenges of the 21st century and help them succeed in the future. Teachers need to incorporate technology into their classrooms. Future education environment requires teachers to acquire general and special knowledge and skills. Pedagogical approaches in the educational system if they remain relevant and successful, there will be several developments in education. Innovative approaches in education should be introduced in pedagogical activity and skills by improving infrastructure, improving English proficiency and online content knowledge and imagination should be expanded. Addressing the shortage of teachers in education, increasing the motivation of teachers, raising awareness of existing pedagogical methods should be used, departmental coordination should be strengthened. Helping to overcome obstacles has a significant impact on the technology that occurs in the process of teaching at all levels of schooling. Thus, it made teaching easier and learning more fun. Helping teachers in their professional development and meeting the diverse needs of all types of learners, will be able to use technology in the Republic of Uzbekistan helps ensure universal access to education. In this respect, the impact of technology on teaching and learning is huge. To teach today's students, educators must recognize the value of integrating technology and different methods and manuals should be used in pedagogy.

Keywords: Higher education system, pedagogical skill, innovation in education, pedagogical methods, technologies in modern education.

Introduction

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the introduction of new and modern technologies in the higher education system is underway. Education affects every element of human life. Nowadays, it is difficult to imagine the education system without technology. As a result of these development and growth, learning standards the twenty-first century will be greater than them. Technology-based learning in the classroom is essential preparing students for the 21st century technologically advanced educational program and preparing them for success we will have paved the way for future endeavors. Teachers should learn new pedagogical methods and new information both general and specialized, to be able to live and should create priorities for success in the future educational environment. Skills of teachers is the effective use of technology in the classroom. In the education system is called pedagogical competence. Qualified teachers technological pedagogy should study this knowledge. As a result, the program of using modern technologies in the educational system an easier and more effective learning experience for creates opportunities for students. Three pillars of pedagogy in education content, pedagogy and technology. In addition to modern computers in the educational system, the Internet, digital video and projectors every day, technology such as books and whiteboards can be used. Regarding specialization in education learning and applying "pedagogy". there are educational theories, methods and procedures. As for the higher education system in the Republic of Uzbekistan, pedagogues use various methods to increase student interest and attention to the lesson. By now, boring lectures have decreased. Students now have options to watch videos or search for interesting information on the Internet. Such lessons retain 60% of the topic in the student's memory, and 20% of the topic remains in the student's memory when working independently. Today, most industries are operating on the basis of technology. As we all know, innovation is at the center development of every society is important. Innovation helps general growth and improvement the quality of any process, product, service or idea done. It exists in every human society inventions are found to be different forms and degrees, with varying degrees distribution is ensured. Innovative methods of education and educational process more relevant, interesting and valuable through the use of different types of technology and can be explained by methodologies. Stakeholders in Education the education system must keep them up to date. In education knowledge, skills and abilities to implement it is necessary to use new methods based on innovative pedagogical ideas and approaches. There are new pedagogical approaches developed as a result of moving away from

remembering focused on memory and development more skill-based knowledge. Teachers a combination of subject matter expertise, teaching and learning methods and technological pedagogy of educational design environments that foster creativity and should develop innovation among students. Teachers can attract students' attention and through pedagogy. By allowing students to remember all the views presented to them, education the technique of teaching theoretical concepts helps and students improve their memorization skills. When innovative education is students they must remember all the subject concepts available. Innovative pedagogy in the higher education system requires involvement classroom experiences as well as mutual respect relationships between teachers and students. The goal helping students build their existing ones knowledge and skills, development and design, and providing training programs for teachers meaningful to and relevant to students needs and cultures should be addressed. Innovative pedagogical skills help students making teaching more attractive through development new methods of teaching teachers and will be an assistant to achieve their goals. In addition, various innovative pedagogical strategies provide a solid foundation for skill development and ensures unity and team work among students. "The first step in teaching students is to provide and opportunities for teachers to be innovators it's up to them." Teachers with a passion for education continuously offers innovative methods and they give new instructions to their students. All teachers have their own teaching style based on their belief in the role they play in teaching and should ensure the meaningful passage of the educational process. Some prefer the effectiveness of a didactic approach, where content is delivered through lectures or other written materials. Others may take a more student-centered approach, where content is delivered through lectures or other means. Others may still use a student-centered approach that uses inquiry-based activities, others may prefer a more collaborative environment where students interact with each other and the teacher reflects. As part of our series on pedagogy, we're taking a deep dive into the definition of pedagogy and what it means. Teachers often talk about their pedagogical approach. Pedagogy is simply defined as a method and practice will consist of improving the quality of teaching. It includes assessment of teaching methods, teaching theory and feedback. When people talk teaching pedagogy, they refer to the way teachers deliver curriculum content to the classroom. When planning a lesson, the teacher considers different ways to convey the content. The decision will be and based on their teaching preferences, experience and the context in which they

teach. Pedagogy often described as an act of teaching. The pedagogy adopted by teachers shapes their actions, reasoning and other teachings. In the education system strategies based on learning theories, learners' understandings and their needs will consist of the backgrounds and interests of individual students. Its goals may include the development of liberal education (general development of human potential) to the narrower characteristics of vocational education (giving and receiving special skills). Traditional Western pedagogy sees the teacher as the possessor of knowledge and the student as the recipient of it knowledge, but pedagogical theories increasingly define the student as the agent and the teacher as the facilitator. Pedagogical management:

Pedagogical management is a specific type of activity of all subjects of the educational process. It is intended to use methods of goals and forms to support its functioning and development as a pedagogical system. According to research, pedagogical management is inextricably linked with certain effects and is necessary for them. High implementation of the target criteria of the educational process: keeping (working) within the established limits or transition to a new state (development). According to the author, this type of management is aimed at regulation to take the educational process to a higher level. Defines the essence of management in the educational system optimizing it, which provides the following conditions for solving it:

*Planning of Integrated Tasks in Education.

*Specification of the components of the educational process according to the chosen model in education.

*Comparative assessment of different ways of the educational process in terms of situational adequacy.

In general, language teaching and learning has always been open to constant change. Because there was a shift from a descriptive to a more critical view of language, new approaches to teaching emerged and language learning and the social practices that characterize such activities. These approaches consist of critical pedagogy changes to a more revolutionary critical side. Because it relies on the memory of caution thoughtful and analytical learning, creative pedagogical practices are urgently needed use among students. Current concentration of students not in getting good grades is to understand the topics. Team spirit and Since competition, cooperation is also weak it takes precedence over cooperation. Attention should be transferred to the specific character of the learner are requirements based on interests and intelligence. More focus than relying on teachers should be placed in self-study. As a result, the focus needs to

change innovative pedagogical strategies by introducing innovative skills among students, such as creativity, critical thinking, reasoning, communication, problem solving, cooperation skills and other abilities, all of which are important in the current scenario. However, the successful integration of technology and pedagogy offers many advantages. In order to transform students into productive citizens, teachers must share their knowledge with them. Students it is necessary to eliminate obstacles and strengthen their pedagogical talents.

Conclusions

Determining the type of education that meets the needs of teachers and is available is very important in the higher education system. In higher education has the greatest impact on teachers' understandings, practices and readiness for change. Teacher training programs should take into account prior knowledge and teachers' learning experiences, their unique teaching needs, demands should be listened to and conditions should be created. Requirements may vary depending on length of experience, confidence in teaching role. In the educational program mastering reading and so on. In addition, creating conditions for effective professional activity development programs is a difficult but necessary task for higher education. In education institutions that have been reviewed earlier and reviewed in this article. Education limitations on the collection of personal and academic information about participants further quantitative analyses, including research section shows the influence of the types of courses they took and their teaching experience on their perceptions of the training they received. It can be an important focus and will be meaningful information for future research. Future work should also consider self- and peer-assessed learning. It is also important to go deeper in empirical understanding and provision and in education evidence about the conceptual framework and objectives of the curricula and models of training programs developed by training centers and are different from educational or academic structures in higher education institutions. On the other hand, it should also include qualitative data from monitoring the established dynamics. In education it is necessary to organize discussions between the participants during training sessions. A change in the methodology of an action research or laboratory intervention may be useful to track these teachers' future moments. This is a pedagogue's enhances the process of professional development. The results of learned knowledge are always strongly contextualized by Students shared knowledge with each other while organizing discussions in their brainstorming processes.

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